

SOCIAL NETWORKS AS A FACTOR IN SHAPING YOUTH LEISURE PRACTICES IN THE DIGITAL ERA

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Abstract. *The article examines the main aspects of consuming content created by bloggers and the role of virtual platforms in shaping cultural identity and social connections. The article presents the results of empirical studies demonstrating a high degree of involvement of young people in the virtual space, as well as the positive and negative consequences of active use of social networks. The need for further study of this phenomenon to optimize the use of digital technologies in the educational and social spheres is emphasized.*

Keywords: *youth, youth culture, identity, social networks, internet addiction*

In the context of globalization, social networks and blogospheres have become an integral part of the daily life of young people, forming new models of communication and leisure. The youth of Karakalpakstan, in particular, actively use these platforms to exchange information, express themselves and communicate with like-minded people. Virtual spaces open up unique opportunities to learn about traditional culture, modern trends and lifestyle, and also contribute to the formation of new social connections. The purpose of this study is to analyze the impact of social networks and blogs on the organization of youth leisure in Karakalpakstan and to identify trends emerging in the process of digital transformation.

According to the information received from the respondent Baltabayev Bauyrzhan, social networks such as Instagram play an important role in the lives of modern people, providing them with ample opportunities for self-expression and business development. In particular, Baltabayev Bauyrzhan, who is engaged in traditional craft - making yurts, uses social networks to maintain a personal blog and distribute his creations around the world: This allows me not only to preserve and popularize the family tradition, but also makes my work more accessible to a wider range of people. In addition, social networks provide an opportunity for free or low-cost advertising and business promotion. Many young entrepreneurs use these platforms to attract new customers, improve the company's image and maintain interaction with existing customers. In this case, social networks become an important tool for self-realization, preserving cultural heritage and developing business in the modern world.[1] They contribute to the expansion of social connections, increasing the availability of information and promoting goods and services. In the course of a comprehensive study, including both ethnographic and sociological methods, a survey was conducted among the youth of the Republic of Karakalpakstan to study their attitudes toward social networks.

According to the data obtained, 52% of young people consider the use of social networks useful, 25.4% consider it a waste of time, and 22.7% found it difficult to answer. Despite the fact that most young people positively assess the role of social networks, there is also a significant proportion of those who perceive them as an ineffective pastime, which may negatively affect their future. Moreover, when answering the question "Why do you use social networks?", 71.1% of respondents indicated that they use them for work, study, and searching for information, while

28.9% noted personal goals. These results indicate that social networks serve more as educational and professional tools than as means of personal communication [2].

The data presented demonstrates the dual nature of the perception of social networks by the youth of Karakalpakstan: on the one hand, they are recognized as useful and necessary for study and work, on the other hand, there is a certain amount of skepticism regarding their effectiveness and appropriateness of use. This emphasizes the importance of further studying this phenomenon and developing recommendations for optimizing the use of social platforms in educational and professional activities. According to respondent Ilkhambayev Islam, social networks provide access to a huge amount of information, which allows users to keep abreast of the latest events and develop in various fields: Social media platforms provide access to educational resources, online courses and professional communities where people can share knowledge and acquire new skills, which contributes to self-education and professional development.

The study also showed that almost all young people in Karakalpakstan use social networks primarily through smartphones. Thus, 95.3% of respondents indicated that they most often access the Internet from mobile devices, while 3.9% use computers and laptops, and 0.8% use tablets (Appendix No. 5). Another aspect revealed during the study was the preference of young people for different types of games. According to the data obtained, 49.2% of respondents prefer sports games, 30.1% - computer or mobile games, while only 20.7% chose traditional Karakalpak games. These results demonstrate the growing popularity of virtual games among the younger generation, while interest in sports games remains.

Moreover, many computer and mobile games also contain social networking components that allow players to communicate with each other in virtual space by exchanging messages, audio and video recordings. According to respondent Sultanbek Adenbayev, such interaction can contribute to the study of foreign languages and acquaintance with the cultures of other countries: In Karakalpakstan, many young people now play games such as Dota, Clash of clans, Counter strike, Pubg mobile in their free time, during which they communicate with people from other countries and many have learned to speak Russian and English thanks to such communication, thereby enriching their language skills.

This survey demonstrates the multifaceted nature of the role of social networks in the lives of modern youth in Karakalpakstan, where they act not only as a communication tool, but also as a means of access to information, education and new cultural practices.

Of course, when considering the role of social networks in the lives of young people, it is necessary to take into account their negative aspects. One of the most alarming examples is the so-called Blue Whale game, first mentioned in 2015 in Russia and the CIS countries. This closed group on social networks offered participants to go through a kind of "quest", the final stage of which was suicide. This phenomenon caused a wide public outcry and attracted the close attention of law enforcement agencies.

Currently, active measures are being taken to combat such destructive communities. Social networks, under the influence of public opinion, have begun to massively block and delete such groups, which contributes to a gradual improvement in the situation.

However, this example clearly demonstrates that, along with positive opportunities, social networks can also pose serious threats, especially for the vulnerable category of users, which

includes young people. Careful monitoring and timely prevention of such dangerous phenomena are necessary, as well as educational work among young people on the safe use of the Internet.

To overcome Internet addiction and its negative consequences, a comprehensive approach is required, including not only medical, but also psychological, pedagogical, socio-cultural and technological measures. It is necessary to develop effective methods for diagnosing, correcting and preventing excessive addiction to the Internet, as well as to implement programs to develop digital literacy and a culture of using information and communication technologies.

Based on our survey among young people, it was revealed that 65.2% of respondents consider themselves independent from the Internet, while 34.8% admit to having Internet addiction. These results demonstrate that the problem of excessive addiction to social networks and virtual space is also relevant for the youth of Nukus.

In addition, during the interview, respondent Bazarbayev Makhmud confirmed the existence of Internet addiction and pointed out its negative consequences. In his opinion, excessive use of social networks can lead to loss of time and decreased productivity, negatively affecting the quality of life of young people.

Analyzing the results of the survey, we can highlight a number of negative aspects associated with Internet addiction and excessive use of social networks. Firstly, constantly comparing oneself with other users, who often demonstrate only the “ideal” side of their lives in their publications, can lead to a feeling of personal inadequacy and dissatisfaction. This perception of oneself through the prism of social networks has a negative impact on the self-esteem of young people.

Secondly, social networks are becoming a channel for disseminating unverified information and fake news. This can contribute to the manipulation of public opinion and the undermining of trust in reliable sources of information in general. This trend poses a serious threat to the development of critical thinking and media literacy among young people.

Thirdly, constant notifications and the need to update the feed on social networks often act as a distraction that interferes with concentration and productive performance of educational or work tasks. Thus, excessive passion for virtual communication can negatively affect the academic and professional performance of young people.

It should be noted that these negative consequences are closely interconnected and reinforce each other, which together create serious risks for the well-being of young people. A comprehensive solution to these problems requires the implementation of targeted measures at the individual, institutional and societal levels, including the development of digital literacy and a culture of responsible use of information technology.

Conclusion: Summarizing the survey and analysis of empirical data, we can highlight the key motives that motivate young people to communicate in virtual network communities. These include: cognition, communication, affiliation, cooperation, recreation, play, self-realization and self-affirmation. These results indicate that the Internet, having gone from being a communication environment for professional programmers, has transformed into a space for realizing a wide range of interests. The listed motives are expressed in various forms of cooperation in virtual communities: receiving advice, providing assistance to other members, exchanging information and experience. Thus, the results of the study suggest that virtual network communities act as a tool for solving social and personal problems for a significant part of the youth of Nukus, and for some - a source of entertainment and leisure.

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